

REFRACTIVE INDEX OF SUBSTANCES. PART I: VALUE OF n_D^{20} BY EXTRAPOLATION

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The refractive index of 12 halogen and halogen-nitroaromatic compounds has been determined at different temperatures. The temperature coefficient for this type of compounds is found out to be 0.00045. It is suggested that from the value of refractive index at any temperature and a knowledge of this temperature coefficient, the value at 20°, of sufficient accuracy, can be calculated by extrapolation.

For determining the value of Refractor, a physical constant, recently suggested (Joshi and Tuli, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 837) it is necessary to know the refractive index of a substance at 20°. Compounds which are solid at this temperature naturally present difficulties and the values in their cases have to be arrived at by some indirect method.

According to the methods suggested so far, the value may be obtained from the refractivity expressions of Lorentz-Lorenz, Gladstone-Dale, Eykeman etc. or from solutions. The values for 20° calculated from the different refractivity expressions are not satisfactory and vary perceptibly when calculated from readings taken at wide ranges of temperature (Falk, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1913, 82, 504; Eisenlohr, *Ber.*, 1921, 54, 2857). The various solution formulae suggested give divergent results and require further investigation.

As the temperature coefficient of refractive index (dn/dt) for each class of compounds is more or less constant, it should be possible to extrapolate the value at 20° from the experimental values in the fused state and a knowledge of dn/dt .

In the case of aromatic hydrocarbons the temperature coefficient of refractive index, determined by Auwers and Kolligs (*Ber.*, 1921, 55, 21), is of the order 0.00045. We have determined the refractive index at different temperatures of a few liquid aromatic halogen compounds and also of some fused nitro-halogen derivatives of benzene and find that in case of all the substances examined, the value dn/dt is on the average 0.00045. The results of our observations are given in the table below.

TABLE I

o-Dichlorobenzene.			o-Chlorotoluene.		
Temp.	Observed n_D .	Diff. for 10 rise.	Temp.	Observed n_D .	Diff. for 10° rise.
20°	1.5505	...	20°	1.5267	...
30°	1.5461	0.0044	30°	1.5220	0.0047
40°	1.5416	0.0045	40°	1.5174	0.0046
50°	1.5370	0.0046	50°	1.5128	0.0046
60°	1.5324	0.0046	65°	1.5055	0.0048
.	1.5278	0.0046	70°	1.5030	0.0049

TABLE I (contd.)

Temp.	Observed n_D .	Diff. for 10° rise.	Temp.	Observed n_D .	Diff. for 10° rise.
<i>m</i> -Dichlorobenzene.			<i>m</i> -Chlorotoluene.		
20°	1.5464	...	20°	1.5224	...
30°	1.5420	0.0044	30°	1.5179	0.0045
35°	1.5399	...	40°	1.5135	0.0044
40°	1.5377	0.0043	50°	1.5099	0.0045
45°	1.5356	0.0043	55°	1.5063	...
50°	1.5333	0.0044	60°	1.5041	0.0049
55°	1.5311	0.0045	65°	1.5015	0.0048
60°	1.5289	0.0044	70°	1.4992	0.0049
65°	1.5265	0.0046	75°	1.4968	0.0047
70°	1.5240	0.0049			
1:2:4-Trichlorobenzene. ^c			<i>p</i> -Chlorotoluene.		
20°	1.5714	...	20°	1.5209	...
30°	1.5669	0.0045	30°	1.5165	0.0044
40°	1.5625	0.0044	40°	1.5122	0.0043
50°	1.5582	0.0043	50°	1.5078	0.0044
55°	1.5561	...	60°	1.5031	0.0047
60°	1.5537	0.0045	70°	1.4984	0.0047
65°	1.5515	0.0046	80°	1.4936	0.0048
70°	1.5492	0.0045			
75°	1.5468	0.0047			
80°	1.5446	0.0046			
<i>o</i> -Chloronitrobenzene (m. p. 32°).			<i>m</i> -Chloronitrobenzene (m. p. 44°).		
35°	1.5647	...	50°	1.5560	...
40°	1.5624	...	55°	1.5538	...
45°	1.5600	0.0047	60°	1.5515	0.0045
50°	1.5578	0.0046	65°	1.5493	0.0045
55°	1.5555	0.0045	70°	1.5469	0.0046
60°	1.5533	0.0045	75°	1.5446	0.0047
70°	1.5487	0.0046	80°	1.5421	0.0048
			85°	1.5397	0.0049
1:4-Dichloro-2-nitrobenzene (m. p. 54°)			1-Chloro-4-bromo-2-nitrobenzene (m. p. 66°) ₄		
55°	1.5673	...	60°	1.5699	...
60°	1.5651	...	65°	1.5677	...
65°	1.5627	0.0046	70°	1.5654	0.0045
70°	1.5605	0.0046	75°	1.5630	0.0047
75°	1.5581	0.0046	80°	1.5607	0.0047
80°	1.5559	0.0046	85°	1.5584	0.0046
85°	1.5536	0.0045			
1-Chloro-2:4-dinitrobenzene (m. p. 54°).			1:2-Dichloro-4:6-dinitrobenzene (m. p. 57°).		
45°	1.5924	...	60°	1.5923	...
50°	1.5902	...	65°	1.5900	...
55°	1.5881	0.0043	70°	1.5878	0.0045
60°	1.5857	0.0045	75°	1.5852	0.0048
65°	1.5833	0.0048	80°	1.5832	0.0046
70°	1.5810	0.0047	85°	1.5807	0.0045
75°	1.5786	0.0047	90°	1.5786	0.0046
80°	1.5763	0.0047			

From a knowledge of the variation of refractive index per degree, we calculated by extrapolation the value of n_D^{20} from the observed values at higher temperature and found in the case of all the liquids a very close agreement between the calculated and the

observed values. As the extrapolated values for refractive index in case of liquids agree with the observed values, in our opinion, the values for solids at 20°, obtained by extrapolation from the experimental values in the fused state, can also be presumed to be correct. This assumption is borne out by the direct observations made in case of 1-chloro-2:4-dinitrobenzene and *o*-chloronitrobenzene when the observed values at 20°, (which could be taken due to supercooling) were found to be in close agreement with the extrapolated values.

The following values for n_D^{20} have thus been derived:

1-Chloro-2:4-dinitrobenzene	...	...	1.6037
1:2-Dichloro-4:6-dinitrobenzene	...	...	1.6103
1:4-Dichloro-2-nitrobenzene	...	...	1.5837
1-Chloro-4-bromo-2-nitrobenzene	...	...	1.6085
<i>o</i> -Chloronitrobenzene	...	...	1.5718
<i>m</i> -Chloronitrobenzene	...	...	1.5695

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